

A qualitative study on equal opportunity in education

Ramazan Burak Kahyaoğlu*, Aysel Şener**, Emra Kaçar***, Semra Canbay Orakcioğlu****, Ali Ünlü*****, Adil Yurtseven*****, Demet Şahan*****

To cite this article:

Kahyaoğlu, B. K., Şener, A., Kaçar, E., Orakcioğlu, S. C., Ünlü, A., Yurtseven, A. & Şahan, D. (2023). A case study on equal opportunity in education. *Journal of Action Qualitative & Mixed Methods Research (JAQMER)*. Volume 2, (Issue 1), 61-73. [Online] www.jaqmeronline.com DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8328361

Article Info: Received: August, 29th, 2023 Revised: September, 5th, 2023 Accepted: September, 7th, 2023

Abstract. This study was conducted to understand and interpret how teachers working in primary schools affiliated with the Ministry of National Education in the provinces of Antalya and Bursa during the 2022-2023 academic year evaluated equal opportunities in education based on their opinions. The research was a qualitative study, and it was designed as descriptive phenomenology. According to the findings of the research, it was highlighted that enhancing technological equipment (such as smart boards, tablets, etc.) for students' access to education, opening libraries in schools, and taking measures to reduce student absenteeism were necessary. The research findings also concluded that teachers' instructional strategies played a significant role in providing equal opportunities in education to students. Collaborative teaching strategy stood out as the least utilized method. The reasons behind disparities in student achievement include parental attitude, intelligence level, environment, and the education curriculum. Suggestions were made to continue activities like Remedial Education Course (DYK), Primary School Enrichment Program (İYEP), and Supportive Education to reduce achievement disparities. Additionally, it was found that instructional materials such as reference books were necessary to reduce achievement disparities.

Keywords: Equality, opportunity, education, technology

Introduction

Society consists of individuals who come together in a natural environment within certain limits to pursue common goals, engaging in relationships, cooperation, and solidarity based on rules (Başaran, 1989). To regulate these relationships and maintain the cohesion of society, structures called institutions have been established. Institutions such as health, family, education, science, politics, law, religion, and ethics constitute the fundamental building blocks of society. There needs to be a harmonious collaboration among these institutions. For instance, shortcomings within the healthcare institution (e.g., insufficient dissemination of disease prevention information) can lead to overcrowding in hospitals. Similarly, deficiencies within the education and science institutions can also impact other institutions (Toprakçı, 2017).

One of the most important institutions of society is the education system. Education is a process through which an individual consciously and intentionally brings about the desired change in their behavior through personal experience (Ertürk, 1975). Additionally, education encompasses the transmission of culture and plays a significant role in nurturing individuals who possess the qualities that contribute to

* Akdeniz University, Antalya, Turkey, burakcan0071985@gmail.com, 0000-0002-2268-4162

**Ministry of National Education, Antalya, Turkey, seneraysel649@gmail.com, 0009-0000-8637-4844

***Ministry of National Education, Bursa, Turkey, emrasilah2@gmail.com, 0009-0005-1074-8885

****Ministry of National Education, Antalya, Turkey, semra.orakcioglu@gmail.com, 0009-0005-7346-8186

*****Ministry of National Education, Antalya, Turkey, hantugral611@gmail.com, 0009-0000-7208-0677

*****Ministry of National Education, Antalya, Turkey, adilyurtseven07@gmail.com, 0009-0008-2269-3916

*****Ministry of National Education, Antalya, Turkey, demetaktepe@hotmail.com, 0009-0001-9619-2152

the continuation and strengthening of the current political system within society (Sabancı, 2016).

The concept of equality in education refers to every individual's right to equal access to educational services and the establishment of equal opportunities in education. The notion of equality aims to create an environment within the education system where differences are acknowledged, but these differences do not hinder individuals from accessing educational services or achieving success in education (Özkan, 2017).

To achieve equality in education, individuals should not face discrimination based on their socio-economic status, gender, ethnic background, or other individual differences. They should have equal access to the same educational opportunities. Equality in education is a necessary condition for each individual to discover and develop their potential (Sönmez, 2013).

The concept of opportunity in education refers to ensuring equal opportunities for individuals to access educational services and succeed in education. This concept aims for all individuals within the education system to have equal access to educational opportunities and benefit from educational services without discrimination (Bursalıoğlu, 2014).

To achieve equal opportunities in education, individuals should have equal access to education without facing discrimination due to their socio-economic status, gender, ethnic background, or other differences. For this purpose, all forms of discrimination should be prevented within the education system, and individuals' differences should be respected. The concept of equal opportunities in education not only guarantees individuals' right to equal access to educational services but also aims to provide them with equal possibilities to achieve success in education. Therefore, equal opportunities in education are essential for ensuring social justice and enabling each individual to fully utilize their potential (Uysal, 2017).

Equality of opportunity in schools is a concept aiming for every student to have the same chances in education. This notion seeks to eliminate opportunities that vary based on factors such as where students are born, their genders, races, or families. Schools can utilize various methods to promote equality of opportunity. These methods may include special programs tailored for different student groups, scholarships, and providing learning materials that suit students' needs (Jackson, 2018).

Equality of opportunity in schools is not only essential for students but also for educational institutions. Achieving equality of opportunity positively impacts students' academic achievements and enhances the quality of the education system. Additionally, it grants students more equal opportunities in societal life. However, achieving equality of opportunity may not always be straightforward. Particularly, resolving differences among students requires significant effort. Yet, through these endeavors, a fairer education system and society can be achieved (Lareau, 2015).

Equality of opportunity aims to eliminate disadvantages arising from students' economic, social, cultural, and geographical differences. In this context, schools can implement various strategies to bridge these gaps among students. For instance, educational institutions can offer additional support programs for disadvantaged students. Furthermore, schools can identify potential obstacles students might encounter during their educational journey and develop policies to remove these barriers. By doing so, students can have equal opportunities in education, fostering a more equitable society (Lucas, 2011).

The fundamental purpose of studies related to equality of opportunity is to ensure that individuals from all walks of life have equal access to opportunities and the chance to fully realize their potential. Economic, social, cultural, and geographical disparities within society can create inequalities in education, leading some students to experience failures, dropouts, or unemployment. This study, distinct from other research on equality of opportunity, aimed to propose concrete strategies to reduce inequalities in education systems in order to enhance the academic success of disadvantaged students. Thus the objectives of this study were to analyze the views of teachers on measures taken for equal opportunities in access and participation for all students, the teaching strategies teachers used to ensure

equal opportunities in education, differences in achievement among students in their schools and the reasons behind these differences, support programs offered to address differences in student achievement and the teaching materials and resources teachers used to address differences in student achievement.

Method and paradigm of research

This study was grounded in practical knowledge and structured in accordance with the interpretive paradigm based on individuals' subjective and intersubjective perspectives (Gunbayi & Sorm, 2018; Gunbayi & Sorm, 2020; Gunbayi, 2020 a,b). The research adopted a qualitative approach, aiming to examine perceptions about "equal opportunities in education" currently ongoing in Turkey through individual interviews with participants. Additionally, the study encompassed equal opportunity measures taken for students' access to education, teaching strategies employed by teachers to ensure equal opportunities, reasons behind variations in student achievements, instructional materials used to address these differences, and support programs offered to bridge these gaps among students. The study followed a qualitative and descriptive phenomenological design. Phenomenological research aims to comprehend and interpret the meanings individuals construct in their minds, emphasizing their perspectives and experiences related to these perceptions (Creswell, 1998; Patton, 1990; Polkinghorne, 1989).

In such research, the researcher interprets the phenomenon in its natural setting, as understood by those involved, by working directly within the natural environment (Denzin & Lincoln, 2012).

Sampling

The sampling of the research consisted of 16 teachers who voluntarily participated in the study, working in schools affiliated with the Ministry of National Education in Antalya and Bursa provinces during the 2022-2023 academic year.

During coding, the names of the participant teachers were not disclosed; 16 (sixteen) voluntary teachers participated. The participants were coded as P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, P8, P9, P10, P11, P12, P13, P14, P15 and P16 according to the order of the interviews.

Table 1.

Distribution of demographic variables of the participants

Theme	Code	Participants
Age	20-30	P6
	31-40	P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P8, P9, P10, P11, P12, P14, P15, P16
	41-50	P13
	51 ve üzeri	P7
Gender	female	P1, P2, P4, P6, P8, P10, P11, P12, P13, P14, P16
	male	P3, P5, P7, P9, P15
Marital Status	single	P4,
	married	P1, P2, P3, P5, P6, P7, P8, P9, P10, P11, P12, P13, P14, P15, P16
Educational Background	Bachelor's Degree Graduate	P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P8, P9, P10, P11, P12, P13, P14, P16
	Master's Degree Graduate	P6, P7
	Doctorate Degree Graduate	P15

Years of Professional Experience	1-5	P6
	6-10	P1, P4, P9, P10, P11, P16
	11-15	P2, P3, P5, P8, P12, P14
	16-20	P13, P15
	21 and +	P7
Years of Service in the Institution	1 year -	P4, P10
	1-3 year	P1, P5, P6, P7, P9, P12, P14, P15, P16
	4-7 year	P2, P3, P11
	8 and +	P8, P13
Subject/Field	Mathematics Teacher	P4, P6, P9
	Religious Culture Teacher	P13
	Turkish Language Teacher	P3, P12
	English Teacher	P2, P8, P10
	Social Studies Teacher	P5
	Classroom Teacher	P1, P7, P11, P14, P15, P16
City of Employment	Bursa	P2, P3, P4, P6, P7, P8, P11, P12
	Antalya	P1, P5, P9, P10, P13, P14, P15, P16

Data collection

The data collection process employed a strategy in which the researcher conducted face-to-face interviews with the participants to gather data. The collected data were analyzed in detail using descriptive analysis method. The main aim of descriptive analysis was to reach concepts and relationships that explain the collected data. The data were first conceptualized, then logically organized based on emerging concepts, and themes explaining the data were identified

The obtained data were presented to a subject expert and three teachers from two different types of schools for code determination. Similarities between the codes generated in the research and those provided by the experts were identified. To examine the inter-coder reliability, the coefficient of agreement between the coders was calculated, as for the reliability of coding, at least two independent coders were required (Neundorf, 2002).

Ethical Procedures

Ethics Committee Approval of this research was obtained from Akdeniz University Social Sciences Ethics Committee at the meeting of 13 decision numbered 312 on June 8th, 2023, informed consent form was obtained from the participants before the interview and participants were informed that their names would not be mentioned and be given the alphabetical codes as P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, P8, P9, P10, P11, P12, P13, P14, P15, and P16.

Validity and Reliability of the Research

The internal and external validity and reliability of the qualitative data were increased based on the criteria of credibility, transferability, confirmability and dependability (Lincoln & Guba, 1985): the semi-structured interview form was developed by the review of the relevant literature for credibility and for confirmability the themes of the transcripts were nodded by two independent researchers (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Cohen, Mannion & Morrison, 2007, Gunbayi, 2018).

In the research, assistance was sought from two researchers specialized in educational management. The inter-coder agreement percentage was calculated using the formula "Reliability = Agreement / (Agreement + Disagreement) x 100" (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

The agreement percentage between the coders was calculated as 74.81%. The findings obtained in

accordance with the research purpose were presented with direct quotes from teacher opinions to provide support. Descriptive analysis method was used in the data analysis. Descriptive analysis is a systematic, repeatable technique in which specific words in a text are summarized into smaller descriptive categories based on specific rules (Büyüköztürk, *et al.* , 2014).

Data Analysis

The interviews were carried out by the researcher and recorded as audio files, transcribed verbatim and their accuracy was confirmed by the participants. The answers to the questions were coded and thematic, descriptive analysis were done via NVIVO software (Kelle, 1995; Cohen, Mannion & Morrison, 2007). In conclusion and discussion, the findings were interpreted and discussed.

Findings

1. Participants' views on measures taken for equal opportunities in access and participation for all students

The findings regarding the measures taken for students' access to education and equal opportunities are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

The measures for equal opportunities

Theme	Codes	Participants
Use of Technological Equipment and Materials	Usage of Smart Boards	P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P8, P9, P14, P15
Attendance and Absenteeism	Ensuring Students' School Attendance	P1, P8, P11, P12, P14, P15
Supporting Students	Supporting Economically Disadvantaged Students (books, stationery, clothing)	P5, P8, P14, P13
Taking Necessary Measures for Foreign National Students	Providing Separate Classes for Foreign Students to Learn Turkish	P10, P11
Creating an Appropriate Educational Environment According to Students' Levels	Referring Gifted Students to Relevant Institutions, Full-time Inclusion Education for Special Needs Students	P10, P11
Adapting Classrooms Appropriately	Adapting Classrooms into Suitable Learning Environments	P15, P7
Establishing a School Library	Opening the Library for Student Use	P6
Conducting Practice Exams to Assess Students' Levels	Conducting Practice Exams	P13

When evaluating the opinions regarding the measures taken for equal opportunities for access and participation in education for all students as presented in Table 2; participants expressed their views on themes as Use of Technological Equipment and Materials, 'attendance and absenteeism', 'supporting students', 'taking necessary measures for foreign national students', creating an appropriate educational environment according to students' levels, 'adapting classrooms appropriately', establishing a school library, conducting practice exams to assess students' levels '. The participants' views on the themes are given below:

"We are striving to ensure equal opportunities by effectively using smart boards, which are educational technologies, in our lessons to eliminate learning differences among students." (P2,1)

"We ensure and monitor students' attendance by conducting parent meetings and home visits with students who are reluctant to come to school, either due to family reasons or personal preference." (P11,2)

"Since our school is located in an industrial area, there are abundant job opportunities. This situation leads to a high level of migration to this area. As a result, we have a significant number of foreign national students in our school. To support their adaptation to school and their learning of Turkish, we create separate classes for foreign national students to learn Turkish." (P10,4)

"In order to prevent our students from facing a shortage of both reference books and reading books, we have established a library in our school to ensure their access. Additionally, we provide a secure environment for studying after school hours for students who are interested, aiming to offer opportunities for equal participation." (P6,7)

2. Participants' views on the teaching strategies they use to ensure equal opportunities in education

The findings related to the teaching strategies used by teachers to achieve equal opportunities in education are presented in Table 3.

Table 3.

The impact of teaching strategies on equal opportunities

Theme	Codes	Participants
Presentation-Based Teaching Strategy	Presentation Approach	P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, P8, P9, P10, P11, P12, P13, P14, P15, P16
Discovery-Based Teaching Strategy	Discovery Approach	P2, P7, P8, P10, P11, P12, P14, P15
Research-Inquiry Teaching Strategy	Research-Inquiry Approach	P7, P12, P14
Collaborative Learning Teaching Strategy	Collaborative Group Work Approach	P3, P12, P14

When evaluating the participants' views on the teaching strategies they use to ensure equal opportunities in education as presented in Table 3; they expressed their opinions on themes as 'presentation-based teaching strategy ', 'discovery-based teaching strategy ', 'research-inquiry teaching strategy', and 'collaborative learning teaching strategy ' views on the themes are given below:

"Our classes are quite crowded, so we generally use the presentation approach in our teaching strategy." (P4,1)

"Due to the overcrowded nature of our classes, the discovery approach method does not always provide much opportunity in terms of time, but occasionally, to some extent, I use the discovery approach teaching strategy." (P8,2)

"Since most of our students do not have internet access at home, we have difficulty assigning research assignments; therefore, we cannot effectively use the research-inquiry approach teaching strategy." (P16,3)

"Despite mainly using the presentation approach in our teaching strategy due to the crowded nature of our classes, we also do not neglect to occasionally involve collaborative group activities and strive to actively engage students in the learning process." (P3,4)

3. Participants views on differences in achievement among students in their schools and the reasons behind these differences

The findings related to the reasons behind differences in student achievement are presented in Table 4.

Table 4.

Differences in Student Achievement

Themes	Codes	Participants
Parental involvement, attitude, education, and disciplinary approach, family's socio-economic level, communication with the family	Family Factor	P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, P8, P9, P10, P11, P12, P13, P14, P15, P16
Student's level of intelligence, physical development, readiness level, interest and attitude towards the lesson, student's mental distress and illnesses	Individual Differences	P2, P3, P4, P7, P8, P10, P11, P14
The school being located in an area with high migration, resulting in overcrowded classrooms, school facilities	School Factor	P1, P3, P7, P9, P10, P12,
Student's circle of friends	Environmental Factor	P5, P9, P14
Attitude and behavior of teachers towards students, teacher changes	Teacher Factor	P10, P12, P14,
Curriculum that is not suitable for student level	Curriculum	P10

When evaluating teachers' opinions on the differences in achievement among students in their schools and the reasons for these differences, as presented in Table 4; they expressed their views on themes as 'parental involvement, attitude, education, and disciplinary approach, family's socio-economic level, communication with the family', 'student's level of intelligence, physical development, readiness level, interest and attitude towards the lesson, student's mental distress and illnesses', 'the school being located in an area with high migration, resulting in overcrowded classrooms, school facilities', 'student's circle of friends', 'attitude and behavior of teachers towards students, teacher changes' and 'curriculum that is not suitable for student level'. The participants' views on the themes are given below:

'Our school is located in a region that experiences significant migration due to its geological location. As a result, we have a student profile from all around Turkey. Additionally, we have a considerable number of students from broken families. Parents of our students work in shifts, which unfortunately leads to their inability to spend time with their children or causes communication problems due to their work schedules. This situation significantly affects the students' success in school. I can say that parents who are involved with their children in every aspect tend to have more successful children both in behavior and achievement compared to parents who are less involved.' (P3,1)

'In terms of student achievement, factors such as the student's level of intelligence, readiness, learning gaps in lower grades, interest, and attitude towards the lesson are quite important. Additionally, the psychological distress and illnesses that a child experiences also play a significant role in their success.' (P4,2)

'I believe that the environment plays a crucial role in a student's success. Making the wrong choice of friends, when not recognized, significantly affects a student's success.' (P5,4)

'Teachers' negative attitudes and behaviors towards students significantly discourage students from lessons and school, thereby impacting their success to a considerable extent. Furthermore, the appointment of substitute teachers or their desire to leave mid-term for various reasons causes constant teacher turnover, which makes it challenging for students to adapt to new teachers and significantly affects their success.' (P12,5)

4. Participants' views on support programs offered to address differences in student achievement

The findings related to participants' views on support programs offered to address differences in student achievement are presented in Table 5.

Table 5.

The support programs offered in schools

Themes	Codes	Participants
Remedial and Enrichment Courses (DYK, İYEP) and courses for foreign national students	Courses	P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P7, P8, P9, P10, P11, P12, P13, P14, P15
Mock exams conducted to identify students' learning gaps	Mock Exams	P2, P3, P9, P12, P15
Supportive education programs for students with learning difficulties	Supportive Education	P3, P6, P7, P11, P14
Development of study plans under the guidance of school counselors	Study Program	P14, P12
Homework assignments and follow-up	Assignment	P8, P16
Support program designed specifically for 8th-grade students	Coaching System	P4

When evaluating the opinions regarding the support programs offered by the participants to address the differences in student achievements, as presented in Table 5; they expressed their views on themes as 'remedial and enrichment courses (DYK, İYEP) and courses for foreign national students', 'mock exams conducted to identify students' learning gaps', 'supportive education programs for students with learning difficulties', 'development of study plans under the guidance of school counselors', 'homework assignments and follow-up' and 'support program designed specifically for 8th-grade students'. The participants' views on the themes are given below:

'In order to support students' achievements and eliminate achievement disparities, we inform both students and parents about the opening of remedial and enrichment courses in our school, and take the necessary measures to ensure active participation of students in these courses. The courses offered are particularly significant for students with limited financial means who cannot receive any additional support, aiming to eliminate inequality of opportunity.' (P2,1)

'We provide support education services for students who struggle with learning difficulties, specifically targeting subjects they find challenging.' (P7,3)

'In order to ensure lasting learning, we emphasize the importance of assignments and their follow-up. We assign tasks to students via Eba (Education Informatics Network) to promote their engagement.' (P8,5)

'For 8th grade students, we establish a coaching system to closely monitor their study processes through collaboration between parents, the school, and students.' (P4,6)

5. Participants Views on the Teaching Materials and Resources They Use to Address Differences in Student Achievement

The findings related to participants' views on the teaching materials and resources they use to address differences in student achievement are presented in Table 6.

Table 6.

The teaching materials used

Themes	Codes	Participants
Use of Source Books and Materials	Use of Source Books and Materials	P2,P4,P6,P7,P8,P9,P11,P12,P13,P14,P16
Using Smart Boards	Using Smart Boards	P1,P2,P3,P4,P5,P6,P8,P11
Fun Learning Activities	Fun Learning Activities	P2,P10,P11
Seminars and Excursions	Seminars and Excursions	P7,P10

When evaluating the teachers' views on the instructional materials and resources used to address differences in student achievement as presented in Table 6; they expressed their opinions on themes as 'use of source books and materials', 'using smart boards', 'fun learning activities' and 'seminars and excursions'.

'By distributing reference books to students in the 2022-2023 Academic Year, the Ministry of National Education has eliminated the disadvantage of students facing reference book shortages due to their families' financial constraints.' (P7,1)

'The interactive whiteboards available in our schools allow us to make our lessons more visual and auditory, thus making it easier for students to learn and ensuring the permanence of their learning. Additionally, they contribute to effective time management.' (P3,2) '

Engaging activities such as preparing lesson materials together with students, creating bulletin boards, or developing our own games not only make learning enjoyable for students but also result in more lasting learning since they are at the center of their own learning.' (P2,3)

'By organizing seminars and excursions for students, we continuously maintain their motivation and support their learning motivation.' (P7,4)

Discussion and conclusion

In this section, conclusions were discussed in the light of the findings obtained from the research and suggestions were put forward in line with the findings. The views of the teachers participating in the research were discussed in terms of factors affecting equal opportunities in education, such as the measures taken for students' access to education, the employed teaching strategies, the reasons behind differences in student achievements, support programs offered to address these differences, and the instructional materials and resources used in schools.

According to the research findings, it can be observed that equal opportunity in education is not being achieved in Turkey and that this inequality is increasing. Similar results were found in the study conducted by Özsoy (2016). Özsoy states that equal opportunity in education is not being realized in Turkey and that differentiation is progressively increasing.

Equal opportunity in education has become a significant agenda item in many countries in recent years. Equal opportunity means that every student should have access to the same educational opportunities without being disadvantaged due to personal characteristics or social circumstances. To achieve this

goal, many countries have developed various policies and programs. In this article, a compilation of studies related to equal opportunity in education will be presented. Early childhood education: Early childhood education is crucial for enhancing children's development and learning capacities. Therefore, many countries have developed policies, especially for children from disadvantaged families, to provide early childhood education. Teacher Training Programs: Having qualified teachers is a critical factor for equal opportunity in education. Hence, many countries have developed programs to improve teacher education.

According to the findings of the study conducted by Tekkaya & Akgündüz (2018), it is emphasized that equal opportunities should be provided to students in order to achieve equal opportunity in education, and teaching methods and curriculum should be diversified taking into account students' differences. Similar results are also found in the findings of this research.

Reducing Class Size: Class size is a significant factor affecting students' learning and development. Reducing class size allows for more personalized attention to students and provides a more conducive learning environment. **Digital Educational Tools:** Digital educational tools enrich students' learning experiences and assist teachers in more efficient teaching. As a result, many countries have developed policies to promote the use of digital educational tools. **Scholarship Programs:** Scholarship programs aid disadvantaged students in financing their education. Therefore, many countries have developed scholarship programs to provide educational opportunities for disadvantaged students such as:

Increasing Access and Participation in Education: To achieve equal opportunity in education, it is essential to enhance students' access to and participation in education. For this purpose, many countries have developed policies such as extending access to early childhood education and increasing the compulsory education period in primary schools. Moreover, facilitating school transportation is also a factor that enhances students' participation in education.

Assessment and Monitoring System: To ensure equal opportunity in education, regular monitoring and assessment of students' learning processes are crucial. Therefore, many countries have developed assessment and monitoring systems to track students' achievements and development.

Special Education Programs: Some students have unique learning and developmental needs. Special education programs are designed to address these needs. These programs aim to eliminate learning barriers for students and provide them with tailored educational opportunities.

Social Awareness: Increasing societal awareness about equal opportunity in education is also essential. Raising awareness within society about equal opportunity in education helps in the more effective implementation of policies and achieving better outcomes.

The finding in the research that equal opportunity was a crucial element and that equal opportunity could be reduced when appropriate methods and materials were provided is consistent with similar studies done so far. The achievement of equal opportunity in education is one of the fundamental requirements of a just society, and the absence of equal opportunity poses a problem in terms of social justice. (Şişman, 2019) In order to achieve equal opportunity in education, teachers need to understand students' differences and adapt their teaching methods and materials accordingly. (Ercan, 2017)

In Turkey, in order to achieve equal opportunity in education, it is emphasized that policies should be developed to reduce regional and socio-economic disparities, and teaching materials and resources should be distributed fairly to provide equal opportunities to students. (Öztürk, 2019) The finding of this study regarding Equal Opportunity in Education were parallel with Öztürk's study conducted in 2019.

In conclusion, equal opportunity in education has become a prominent topic on the agenda of many countries. Various initiatives are being undertaken in areas ranging from early childhood education to teacher training programs, reducing class sizes, and implementing scholarship programs. The goal of these efforts is to ensure that every student has access to equal educational opportunities without being

dsadvantaged due to personal characteristics or social circumstances.

Recommendations

Various recommendations are put forward to ensure equal opportunities in education. However, it is important to emphasize that the effective implementation of these recommendations relies on political will and the proper allocation of resources.

In line with the findings, following suggestions were put forward:

Researchers should conduct further research on the topic of equal opportunities to identify existing gaps in this field. Additionally, the outcomes of these studies should be taken into consideration in the formulation and implementation of education policies.

Practitioners should understand students' differences and adapt teaching methods and materials accordingly. Furthermore, in order to provide equal opportunities to students, the distribution of curriculum and resources should be fair.

Policymakers should develop policies to ensure equal opportunities and oversee their implementation. These policies should be designed to reduce regional and socio-economic disparities.

All segments of society should collaborate to achieve equal opportunities in education. Students, teachers, parents, school administrators, non-governmental organizations, and policymakers should establish a shared vision for equal opportunities and work together to implement this vision.

Achieving equal opportunities in education requires time, resources, and patience. Therefore, long-term perspectives should be taken into account, and sustainable policies and practices should be developed.

References

- Başaran, İ. E. (1989). İşletme yönetiminde sosyal sorumluluk [Social responsibility in business management]. *Hacettepe University Journal of Economics and Administrative Sciences*, 7(1), 129-138.
- Bursalıoğlu, Z. (2014). Eğitim Yönetimi [Educational Management]. Ankara: Pegem Academy.
- Büyüköztürk, Ş., Kılıç Çakmak, E., Akgün, Ö. E., Karadeniz, Ş., & Demirel, F. (2014). Bilimsel Araştırma Yöntemleri [Scientific research methods]. Pegem Academy.
- Cohen, L., Mannion, L. and Morrison, K. (2007). *Research methods in education*. UK: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Creswell, J. W. (1998). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five traditions*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (2012). *Introduction: The discipline and practice of qualitative research*. The Sage Handbook of Qualitative Research, 4, 1-19.
- Ercan, F. (2017). Farklı öğrenme ihtiyaçlarına sahip öğrencilerin eğitiminde fırsat eşitliği [Equal opportunity in education for students with different learning needs]. *International Journal of Language Academy*, 5(2), 62-69.
- Ertürk, S. (1975). Eğitim Psikolojisi [Educational Psychology]. Ankara: Yargı Publications.
- Gibson, J. L., Ivancevich, J. M., & Donnelly, J. H. (1991). *Organizations: behavior, structure, processes*. 7th ed. Homewood, IL, Irwin.
- Günbayı, İ. (2000). *Örgütlerde İş Doyumu ve Güdüleme [Job Satisfaction and Motivation in Organizations]*, Özen Yayıncılık. Ankara.
- Gunbayı I. (2018). Developing A Qualitative research manuscript based on systematic curriculum and instructional development. *European Journal of Social Sciences Studies*, 3, 3, 124-153.

- Gunbayi, I. (2020a). Systematic curriculum and instructional development for a mixed methods research: SCID-MMR. *Journal of Mixed Methods Studies*, 1, 1-27.
- Gunbayi, I. (2020b). Knowledge-constitutive interests and social paradigms in guiding mixed methods research (MMR). *Journal of Mixed Methods Studies*, 1, 44-56.
- Gunbayi, I. & Sorm, S. (2020). *Social paradigms in guiding management social development and social research*. Ankara: Pegem Academy.
- Gunbayi, I & Sorm, S. (2018). Social paradigms in guiding social research design: the functional, interpretive, radical humanist and radical structural paradigms. *International Journal on New Trends in Education and Their Implications*, 9, 2, 57-76.
- Jackson, C. K. (2018). Boosting educational attainment and adult earnings among low-income, minority students: evidence from a randomized trial of a college-access program. *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics*, 10,3, 1-40.
- Kelle, U. (1995). *Computer aided qualitative data analysis*. London: Sage Publications.
- Lareau, A. (2015). *Unequal Childhoods: Class, Race, and Family Life*. Oakland, CA: University of California Press.
- Lucas, S. R. (2011). *Nurturing young minds: how to help your child succeed*. New York: Teachers College Press.
- Landis, J. R. & Koch, G. G. (1977). The measurement of observer agreement for categorical data. *Biometrics*, 33(1), 159-174.
- Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. Beverly Hills, CA: Sage.
- Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative data analysis: An expanded sourcebook (2nd ed.)*. Sage Publications.
- Neuendorf, K. A. (2002). *The content analysis guidebook*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Özkan, M. (2017). Eğitimde eşitlik [*Equality in Education*]. Ankara: Pegem Academy.
- Özsoy, A. (2016). Türkiye'de eğitimde fırsat eşitliği sorunu [Problem of Equality of Opportunity in Education in Turkey]. *International Journal of Social Science*, 5(1), 133-147.
- Öztürk, M. (2019). Eğitimde fırsat eşitliği ve türkiye'deki durumu [Equality of Opportunity in Education and Its Situation in Turkey]. *Journal of International Social Research*, 12(63), 122-133.
- Patton, M. Q. (1990). *Qualitative evaluation and research methods (2nd Ed.)*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Polkinghorne, D. E. (1989). *Phenomenological research methods*. In R.S. Valle and S. Halling (Eds.), *Existential-phenomenological perspectives in psychology: Exploring the breadth of human experience* (pp. 41-60). New York: Plenum Press.
- Sabancı, V. (2016). Eğitim ve kültür: İç içe geçmiş kavramlar [Education and culture: Intertwined concepts]. *Eğitim ve Öğretim Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 5(3), 1-4.
- Sönmez, V. (2013). Eğitimde fırsat eşitliği ve eşitlik kavramı [Equality of Opportunity and Concept of Equality in Education]. *Electronic Journal of Social Sciences*, 12(43), 259-276.
- Tekkaya, C., & Akgündüz, D. (2018). Eğitimde fırsat eşitliği sorununa bakış [Perspectives on Equality of Opportunity Issue in Education]. *Kastamonu Education Journal*, 26(1), 25-31.
- Toprakçı, E. (2017). Eğitim kurumunun sosyal ve kültürel açıdan önemi [Importance of the Educational Institution in Social and Cultural Aspects]. *National Education Journal*, 219(231), 117-123.
- Uysal, M. (2017). Eğitimde Fırsat Eşitliği [*Equality of Opportunity in Education*]. İstanbul: Derin Yayınları.

Ethical approval

The study titled "**A Case Study of Equal Opportunity in Education**" adhered to the rules of scientific, ethical, and citation standards during its writing process; the authors of this study affirmed that no falsification was done on the collected data. "Journal Action Qualitative & Mixed Methods Research [JAQMER]" and the Editor hold no responsibility for any ethical violations that may arise, and all accountability rests with the authors. Furthermore, the study has not been submitted for evaluation to any other academic publishing platform.

Ethics committee approval

Ethics Committee Approval of this research was obtained from Akdeniz University Social Sciences Ethics Committee at the meeting of 13 decision numbered 312 on June 4th, 2023.